

T.U. Central Library and its Contribution to Nepal's Higher Education

Prabhu Ray Yadav

Assistant Professor of English, Patan Multiple Campus Patandhoka, Lalitpur, Tribhuvan University, Kathmandu, Nepal

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15710770](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15710770)

Paper History

Received: 12-08-2024

Accepted: 27-08-2024

Published: 15-09-2024

C/A: P. R. Yadav

Abstract: This study investigates the historical and contemporary role of the Central Library of Tribhuvan University, Kirtipur, in the advancement of higher education in Nepal. Established in 2019 B.S., the library has served as a pivotal institution in the nation's academic development, especially during a time when Nepalese students relied on Indian universities for higher education. Using a qualitative approach, this research evaluates the library's contributions to research, teaching, and human resource development, emphasizing the commitment of its staff and administrators. Drawing upon textual evidence from works such as *Grand Story* and *Our Service* of T. U. Central Library by Narayan Prasad Mishra, the study critiques systemic challenges, including corruption and administrative inefficiencies that hinder the library's full potential. By analyzing the library's services, infrastructure, and educational impact, the study highlights its role as a backbone of Nepal's intellectual growth and calls for renewed attention to the moral and functional integrity of institutions supporting higher learning. This research ultimately seeks to reaffirm the library's national significance and promote a vision of higher education rooted in sincerity, equity, and academic excellence.

Keywords: Library's Services, Infrastructure, Educational Impact

BACKGROUND

The research contributes to Nepal's higher education by the Central Library of Tribhuvan University, Kirtipur. Its role in promoting Nepal's higher education is well known to the world. The Central Library has been playing a significant role in the fields of research and teaching since its establishment in BS 2019. Before the establishment of the Central Library, the Nepalese people used to receive higher education from Calcutta, Patna, and Banaras and other most important cities of India. The education system of Nepal, in particular higher education, was initially affiliated to the Universities of Patna, Calcutta and Banaras. The research aims to highlight how both past and current functions of the Central Library are contributing to the nation's higher education through human resource development, including capacity enhancement of library members. This study applies the qualitative method to critique the service and the roles of its dedicated, sincere and

honest employees. One of the objectives of the research is to attract scholars, and to highlight the importance of library and its contribution to higher education in the country. It seeks to prove how the central library stands as a backbone of both nation and its citizens and how Nepal's higher education through the central library is enriched and developed by producing sincere and honest citizens.

The scope of this research tries to find overall development of the nation learnt from the library. The study, on the basis of the qualitative method mentioned above, seeks to further develop the library's contribution to higher education. At present Nepal's higher education continues to struggle because of lack of understanding among many people of the true values of education. Nepal's higher education has remained a slave to its own educated mafia who lack the necessary competence to contribute in the field of higher education, because they are unable to realize the importance of the

educational insights, visions and ideas, which alone would enable them to work honestly and sincerely for enhancing the image of the centers of higher learning. The mafia employs their non-humanistic approach to achieve something trivial. It makes them forget true values of higher education in the glare of short sighted goals and objectives. Their sole purpose is to grab political power. The chief administrative officer, Narayan Prasad Mishra, who served at the Tribhuvan University Central Library and as Chief of T. U. Academic Council, narrates his own experience by writing about the need of the nation and its people. He never compromised with his moral stand as he mentions it honestly and sincerely in his books entitled *Grand Story and Our Service of T. U. Central Library (2018 AD)*, (*T. U. Central Library Ko Gaurabshali Kahani Ra Hamro Seva*), and *Grieve (2023)*, (*Biarha*). He mentions, in his story entitled "Corruption, and the Dishonesty of the Corrupted Investigative Committee," how Nepal's higher education suffered and keeps suffering because of "the negligence of politically motivated people, who considered themselves greater scholars, but with a myopic vision of education, in which the demoralized population of this world is aghast at the role of such people who claim to be highly educated" (311-23). Their aims and objectives weaken their people and prevent them from pursuing moral, fearless, honest and true human goals. The removal of such bad elements from Nepal's higher education is a big challenge.

The proposed study observes and analyses the central library's role in advancing higher education in Nepal, highlighting the significance illuminated by Shanti Mishra and Narayan Mishra's textual evidence, namely, *Grand Story and Our Service of T. U. Central Library (2018 AD)*, (*T. U. Central Library Ko Gaurabshali Kahani Ra Hamro Seva 2075 BS*). The researcher endeavors to explore the contributions of library services in disseminating intellectual knowledge and emphasizes the importance of ensuring equitable access to these resources across all regions of the nation. The library is staffed by a number of administrative and support personnel dedicated to safeguarding its properties and facilitating its research and academic functions. The researcher examines the comprehensive range of activities conducted both within and beyond the library premises. His research article, "*Net Isn't All Solution*," (2012) published in the *Pursuits Journal of English Studies*, also analyzes how the library should contribute to various educational activities. Its perspective is that the library should serve as a quiet and welcoming space, much like a den, providing a peaceful environment conducive to student learning and focus.

The management of infrastructure is not effectively supporting the development of the Tribhuvan University Central Library. One of the key challenges faced by the Central Library in Kirtipur is regulating its operational hours, especially in managing access during both day and night within the span

of twenty-four hours. Undoubtedly, this is a prestigious library of Tribhuvan University, having held historical significance even prior to the university's establishment. Therefore, the researcher seeks to investigate all facets of the library in light of the evolving patterns of development and service enhancement.

THEORETICAL CONCEPT OF THE STUDY

The study employs the method of qualitative approach to examine the impression and impact of Central Library on Nepal's higher education, depicting various reviews made by scholars from home and abroad. These scholars have worked to address challenges associated with several libraries across the world. The research uses both interdisciplinary and multi-disciplinary methodologies as tools and data to assess the progress of research and teaching. These tools and data variously depend on interviews, focus groups, observations, and analysis of textual or visual materials. This focus aims to enhance the effectiveness of teaching and research while analyzing the Central Library's contributions to higher education in Nepal. The study evaluates the library's outputs, providing a dependable framework for assessing its role in the nation's academic realm. It investigates how Central Library employees contribute to research, teaching, and student support to improve higher education of the country. Moreover, the study highlights how these employees, both the specialized staff and the administrative operators, are actively engaged in their responsibilities to support university education. The analysis of its contribution to Nepal's higher education also incorporates Mishra's textual evidence to provide additional context and depth.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The research seeks to analyze the problem related to Nepal's higher education with reference to the role of the Central Library. It evaluates as well as reflects the economic, social, political and cultural condition of its people. The problem can be solved only by sincere and honest attention and effort to deal with the problem. The following is the statement of problem:

- i) How do the nation and its people look at the state of education and its evolution, with the particular reference to the Central Library?
- ii) How do educated people, who have benefited from the Central Library, respond to the existing challenges and opportunities of education?
- iii) How can Nepal's higher education be assisted, revamped and sustained by the Central Library to cater to the country's needs and demands of the people

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study highlights the significance of the Central Library and its contribution to Nepal's higher education. The research aims to promote value-based knowledge on the basis of the significance of the Central Library for the advancement of the nation and its people. Such goals emphasize the following objectives:

- i) To assess educated individuals' responses to educational challenges with reference to the Central Library.
- ii) To understand public perception of education's evolution through the in-depth understanding or knowledge of the role and contribution of the Central Library.
- iii) To strategize reforms in Nepal's higher education including the Central Library to meet national needs.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The study primarily examines the roles and responsibilities of the official bureaucrats in supporting the Central Library and its contributions to higher education in Nepal. In *The Atlas of New Librarianship*, R. David Lankes (2011) deals with a guideline for this new education for library experts. Lankes defines, "a new librarianship based not on books, articles and artifacts but on knowledge and learning; and a new mission for librarians: to improve society through facilitating knowledge creation in their communities"(243). The library, once celebrated for its significance, now faces a challenge, which is compared to a desolate garden inhabited by owls. As a Muslim philosopher Muhammad Mahmud Ghali (1997) asks, "What will happen to the garden in which owls perch on every branch" (21)? Few people's appearance looks to be contributing to the advancement of the Central Library. In this context, Susan Orlean (2018) states: "No one has a comprehensive proposal for the reformation of librarianship" (177). Initially, the Tribhuvan University (T.U.) Central Library consisted of two separate libraries, one in Lal Durbar and another in Tripureshwor, which merged into a single entity in 2019.

Narayan Mishra highlights that libraries function as exhibitions, serving the purpose of research, researchers, and teaching. Within educational institutions, which also include libraries exhibitions and their resources, play a vital role in fostering practical skills and knowledge essential for research. However, significant challenges persist. The library employees perform their duties with dedication, striving to benefit humanity through their institutional roles.

In the same context, Nahid Shirani Bidabadi (2016) emphasizes that "nationally and locally recognized professors

are effective leaders, offering valuable ideas, insights, and strategies to educators committed to excellence in higher education" (170). These professors, who recognized the values of a library, are widely respected within their communities.

The Central Library's history and contributions are spoiled by distressing corruption attributed to unscrupulous groups within Tribhuvan University (T.U.). These corrupt individuals targeted two prominent Central Library figures, Mrs. Shanti Mishra and Narayan Mishra (2018), who served the library from 2021 BS to 2050 BS. Their experiences are documented in their 2018 book, *A Great Story and Our Service to the T.U. Central Library (T.U. Central Library Ko Gorabshali Kahani R Hamro Seva)*, which opens with a subtitle reminiscent of a Nepalese proverb, "A Story of the T.U. Central Library" (*T.U. Kendriyia Pustakalaya Ko Ek Kahani*, pp. 1-30).

Narayan Mishra emphasized that the library served as a hub for students, teachers, and other learners, fostering academic engagement and knowledge exchange. However, the library's policies and administration faced severe mismanagement, calling for an overhaul of its ineffective governance. This lack of proper control has significantly hindered the library's ability to support higher education in Nepal.

Narayan Mishra further recounted his interaction with T. U. Professor of History Bhavneshwor Pageni (2019), who sought insights into the early challenges faced by the Central Library in its contributions to Nepal's higher education. Mishra exceeded Pageni's expectations, providing comprehensive answers and handing over numerous documents, including copies of original papers and letters from the Tribhuvan University Central Library (TUCL) stores, to support his research on Nepal's academic development.

The review chapter highlights the library's vital role in advancing higher education in Nepal while shedding light on the persistent challenges posed by unscrupulous elements. These corrupt elements have undermined the effortful sweating of dedicated officials, faculty members, and staff of Tribhuvan University, obstructing the library's true potential and service to the academic community.

The history of the Central Library serves as a rhetorical inspiration, encouraging researchers to explore its contributions to Nepal's higher education. In the similar context, **David W. Lewis' (2018)** talk looks into "issues of productivity in the library context and how libraries need to explore, discover, and invent in order to remain vital" (19). For the advancement of higher education in Nepal, both national and international researchers have proposed practical solutions to address the library's challenges in supporting research, researchers, and academic study. Narayan Mishra portrays the

state of higher education as chaotic and deeply influenced by political interference.

The status of the Central Library and its contributions to Nepal's higher education remain entangled in the complexities of multi-party political interference. That is how the Central Library continues to struggle as it attempts to rise above the entanglements and muddles of political turmoil.

The study aims to stimulate readers' interest in strengthening the Central Library and its role in advancing Nepal's higher education. Central Library, Nepal's foremost academic library, is actively working to overcome challenges that obstruct its research and educational environment. Established in 1959 AD, the Central Library has now collected on its books shelves over 410,000 volumes, including books, periodicals, and theses. Without meaningful change, similar challenges may continue to affect other universities across the country.

This study focuses on the Central Library's role in Nepal's higher education, particularly how its staff, both experts and the administrative section, influence research and other academic activities. By examining the library's operations, the research aims to provide insights that could enhance higher education in Nepal. The study also evaluates the library's effectiveness, providing a framework to assess its contributions to the nation's academic landscape with reference to Mishra's book entitled (*T. U. Central Library Ko Gaurabshali Kahani Ra Hamro Seva*). Additionally, it investigates how the Central Library staff support research, teaching, and the academia, shedding light on their evolving roles in university education. The scope of the research does not cover physical infrastructures and financial supports of the Central Library.

The study organizes itself into four chapters. They categorized as Introduction, Literature Review, Discussion/Analysis, and Conclusion. Chapter one provides the background, problem statement, objectives, and hypothesis.

Chapter Two reviews its literature related to the role of libraries in university education. Chapter Three deals with the discussion and analysis of evidence and data collected from research. Chapter Four concludes with summary, findings, and further improvement of the Central Library, including future research recommendations for future research.

CONCLUSION

This research focuses on the significance of T.U. Central Library with reference to its contribution to Nepal's higher education and deals with research, educators, and the teaching pedagogy. It emphasizes the practical knowledge necessary for developing libraries and enhancing their contributions to higher education in Nepal. The researcher aims to step up efforts towards history and analysis of education, society, and the well-being of its learned people. Lack of research in library related its insufficiencies have hindered the advancement of higher education in Nepal.

Libraries based data analysis plays a significant role strengthening the quality of education and research support in Nepal's higher education institutions. They help as sources of knowledge facilitate and access to a vast range of relevant sources and materials that ease learning and research. As stated earlier, the progress of modern higher education which began to the institution of Tri-Chandra College in 1918 AD. Since then, higher education has been able to play an attractive role to address Nepal's developmental challenges, including the country's development goals. But, the absence of a strong research culture has hampered the progress in Nepal's higher education. The research meets the gap that is important for Nepal's socio-economic and cultural development through reasonable emphasis on the contribution to be made by institutions of higher learning including libraries such as the Central Library of T. U. This study emphasizes the importance of research, aiding in the improvement and enhancement of the Central Library and its role in advancing Nepal's higher education system.

REFERENCES

- Bidabadi, S. N. Isfahani, N. A. Rouhollahi, A. & Khalili, R. (2016). Effective Teaching Methods in Higher Education: Requirements and Barriers. *Journal of Advance in Medical Education and Professionalism*. 4 (4), 21-30.
- Ghali, M. M. (1997). *Towards Understanding the Ever-glorious Qur'an*, Al-Ahram.
- Lankes, D. R. (2011). *The Atlas of New Librarianship*, Mit. Press.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/8755.001.0001>
- Lewis, W. D. (2018). Reimagining the Academic Library. *IUPUI University Library*. 4. (1), 19-35.
DOI:10.31046/proceedings.2018.52
- Mishra, P. N., Mishra, S. (2018). *A Great Story and Our Service to the T.U. Central Library (T.U. Kendriya*

Pustakalaya Ko Gorabshali Kahani R Hamro Seva),
Kathmandu.

Mishra, P. N. (2023). *Mourn. (BIRAH)*. New Prakashan.

... (2003). *The Boiling Sufferings*. PILGRIMS.

Orlean, S. (2018). *The Library Book*. Simon & Schuster.

Pangeni, Bh. (2019). Kantipur TV HD, Date February 19, 2019.
... (2080). The History of T. U. (BS 2039 – 2079).

Yadav, R. P. (2012). *Net isn't all solution. Pursuits: A Journal of English Studies*, Department of English, Patan Multiple Campus, Patan Dhoka, Lalitpur.